

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: GEORGE****FIRST NAME: LIZETTE****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: Microsoft Office 365 - MSWord on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What are the three core elements required when creating a strong argument?
 - A claim, responses to questions, and objections,
 - A claim, reasons relevant to your claim, and response to questions.
 - A claim, response to questions, and alternative points of view.
 - A claim, reason for accepting it, and the evidence based on those reasons.¹**
2. When researchers use information from other sources, they are likely to avoid plagiarism by.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 58.

- Having someone write a paper with the information and then put your name.
 - Mentioning the source of the information.**²
 - Using the information in quotes, paraphrases, statistics/data, or visuals.
 - Using information without giving credit to the author.
3. What are the critical components that ground and frame a research study?
- Introduction; literature review; research methods; conclusion.
 - Research plan; research data; analysis; references.
 - Problem, purpose, and research questions.**³
 - Introduction; data collection; data analysis; conclusions and recommendations.
4. In considering the order and format of the chapters of a dissertation, which of those chapters involves finding patterns, themes, ambiguities, and inconsistencies in various results?
- Analysis, Interpretation, and Synthesis.**⁴
 - Methodology and Research Approach.
 - Literature Review.
 - Conclusion and Recommendations.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 327.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 85.

5. Please complete the sentence with the most appropriate answer: "Short form" citations may be used for an authority once
- The reader will have little trouble quickly locating the citation.
 - it falls in the same general discussion as an earlier citation.
 - one full citation is provided for the same authority.**⁵
 - it is clear to the reader what is being referenced.
6. Constitutions and other foundational documents are cited in the following order:
- State, Federal, Foreign, and Foundational Documents of International Organizations.
 - Foreign, Federal, State, and Foundational Documents of International Organizations.
 - Foundational Documents of International or Extraterritorial Organizations.
 - Federal, State, Foreign, and Foundational Documents of International Organizations.**⁶
7. What are the primary sources used for the collection of data and evidence to support one's argument?
- Books from reputable university presses and articles or reports that are peer-reviewed.

⁵ Mary Miles Prince, *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, 19th ed. (Cambridge, Mass: Harvard Law Review Association, 2013), 13.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 57.

- Specialized encyclopedias and dictionaries that offer essays written by scholars in a field.
 - Reports of original research in scholarly journals or government and commercial databases.**⁷
 - Letters, diaries, objects, maps, even clothing works of art census or survey.
8. What would you consider the best use of tertiary sources?
- For making a scholarly argument in support of the hypothesis.
 - To get a broad overview of your topic in the early stages of research.**⁸
 - For the collection of data and evidence to make your case.
 - To learn from other researchers.
9. Please choose the appropriate bibliographical format (order of elements) for the following in-text cited quote: “This book has helped generations of students successfully research, write, and submit papers in virtually all academic disciplines.”
- Turabian, Kate L, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. 2018. A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Ninth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
 - Turabian, Kate L, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press**

⁷ Kate L Turabian, 36.

⁸ Ibid., 37.

Editorial Staff. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.⁹

- Turabian, Kate L, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press 2018.
- Turabian, Kate L, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press 2018.

10. The uniform system of approach for formatting legal citations, the order of authorities, and related authority is highlighted in which of the following rules?

- Rule 14 - Administrative and Executive Materials.
- Rule 4 - Short Citation Forms.
- Rule 1 - Structure and Use of Citations.¹⁰**
- Rule 11 - Constitutions.

⁹ Kate L Turabian, 13, 154-168.

¹⁰ Mary Miles Prince, 53-61.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.